

SCOPE AND CHALLENGES OF PANCHAKARMA BLUEPRINT FOR THE PRESERVATION OF HEALTH IN PRESENT ERA

Dr. Karishma Anwar^{*1}, Dr. Kiran M. Goud², Dr. Shreyas D. M.³

^{*1}PG Scholar, ²Professor, ³Assistant Professor

Department of Panchakarma, Sri Kalabyraveswaraswamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.

***Corresponding Author: Dr. Karishma Anwar**

PG Scholar Department of Panchakarma, Sri Kalabyraveswaraswamy Ayurvedic Medical College, Hospital and Research Centre, Bangalore, Karnataka, India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18104379>

How to cite this Article: Dr. Karishma Anwar, Dr. Kiran M. Goud, Dr. Shreyas D. M.*. (2026). Scope and Challenges of Panchakarma Blueprint For The Preservation of Health In Present Era. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Life Science, 12(1), 21–28.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 04/12/2025

Article Revised on 24/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Panchakarma is a time-tested Ayurvedic detoxification and rejuvenation therapy that plays a crucial role in Preventive, promotive and curative healthcare. Panchakarma not only prevents a disease but also enhances overall well-being and vitality of an individual. It is widely recognised personalised and generalised treatment, to improve one's physical, mental and spiritual health, making it a holistic approach to preserve health and prevent future imbalances. In the current era, the scope of Panchakarma has expanded beyond traditional Ayurvedic settings to Integrative medicine, wellness centres and preventive healthcare. However several challenges hinder its widespread adoption. Standardisation of procedures, lack of time, several myths about the holistic therapies, lack of globally accepted guidelines pose significant hurdles. Despite these challenges, Panchakarma holds great promise as a blueprint for sustainable health preservation. By keeping the *srotas* clear and functional, Panchakarma enhances *Dhatu Poshana*, *Ojo vardhana* and overall physiological balance.

KEYWORDS: *Panchakarma*, *Panchakarma* blueprint, Scope, Challenges, Preservation of health.

INTRODUCTION

Preservation of Health means not only the negative blessings of freedom from disease and pain of all sorts. It's not only the physical pleasure chiefly felt in infancy and youth. Starting as early as age 20, our heart and blood vessels tends to gradually change overtime even in healthier state due to the factors like loss of collagen, reduced elasticity of the blood vessels, Hypertension, Chronic inflammation (Endothelial dysfunction). So to maintain the patency of these *Srotas*, there is the requirement of proper *Samshodhana* periodically either in a *Swastha Avastha* or *Atura Avastha* and thus preserve health. As mentioned in the vedas, there are 4 types of Yugas. Among which the present is Kali Yuga. In Kali Yuga life span of human being is max. of one hundred years.^[1] This deterioration in life span is mainly because of the mode of life we are leading currently. Factors responsible for the maintenance of normal life span are, *Prakruti Sampath*, *Guna Sampath*, *Atma Sampath*.^[2]

Excellency of all these will improve quality of one's life. There are nine Domains of wellness, and Panchakarma helps to maintain this wellness by optimum functioning of *Srotas*.

PANCHAKARMA IN MODERN HEALTH PRESERVATION

There are two types of *Swastha*

1. *Bhishak paripalita swastha* (Healthy by routine)
2. *Yadrucchswastha* (Healthy by chance)

The *Samyata* between *Dosha*, *Dhatu* and *Malas* can be achieved by correctly following *Dinacharya* and *Rutucharya*. They are the primordial prevention methods for lifestyle disorders and thus preserving the health. Caution to avoid *Shodhana* in *swastha*, is just like caution to avoid waking up a sleeping poisonous snake makes the rationality behind the performance of *Rutushodhana* debatable one.^[3] But this caution is only

applicable for *Asanchita dosha Swastha* and not for *Sanchita dosha swastha*. *Sanchita dosha swastha* is always indicated for *Shodhana*.

To attain a state of *Samyata* one must get acquainted with few principles as follows

1. *Vruddhih samanaih sarvesham vipareetaih viparyayah.*^[4]
2. *Prajnaparadho hi Sarvaan rogaan janayati.*^[5]

From consumption of food to gaining of energy and posing body for the nutrition to removal of wastes at

systemic level, Interruption of this hierarchy at some stage leads to occurrence of *vyadhi*. The *ama* which circulates in *sarva shreera* with *Rasa dhatu* and the *Sangha* of *Ama* takes place, which leads to *khavaigunyata* and pathogenesis of disease occurs.^[6]

Shodhana works throughout all these stages by its action on *Agni, Srotas and Dosha prakopa sthanas*. Three factors which influences the derangement in a *Swastha* are *Asatmyendriyartha Samyoga, Prajanaparadha and parinama.*^[7]

Table No. 1: Scope of Panchakarmas.

Sl.No.	PANCHAKARMA	SCOPE
1.	<i>Vamana</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If a person undergoes <i>Vamana</i> Periodically, It prevents <i>Kasa, upalepa, swarabheda, nidra, asyadourgandhya etc vyadhis.</i>^[8] • <i>Vamana</i> does <i>Agni vardhana</i>.
2.	<i>Virechana</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Virechana</i> promotes <i>Bala</i> (Strength), <i>Aayush</i>(Longevity), <i>Aamayghna</i>(Destroys ailments).^[9]
3.	<i>Basti</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does <i>Shareeropachaya</i>, imparts <i>Varna, Bala, Arogya, Ayush.</i>^[10]
4.	<i>Nasya</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Removes <i>Indriya Vaimalyata</i>, imparts <i>Bala</i> to <i>Hanu, Danta, Shiras, Greeva, Trika, Bahu & Uras</i>. • Prevents <i>Vali, Paalitya, Khalitya, Vyanga.</i>^[11]
5.	<i>Raktamokshana</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prevents <i>Twak Roga, Granthi, Shopha</i>. • Does <i>Manah Prasadana</i> • Imparts <i>Bala, Varna, Sukha Ayusha.</i>^[12]

Table No. 2: Blueprint of Panchakarma In Pre-Conceptional Health Preservation.

Sl.No.	Karma	Description
1.	Deepana & Pachana	Selection of Drugs having <i>Deepana & Pachana Gunas</i> . Eg- <i>Trikatu Churna, Shunti choorna</i>
2.	Snehana Karma	<i>Ghrta</i> can be Advised (Until <i>Samyak snigdha lakshanas</i> are attained) Eg- <i>Phala Ghrta, Sukumara ghrta, Varunadi ghrta etc.,</i>
3.	Swedana Karma	<i>Madhyama or Mahan Sweda</i> (Considering <i>Rogi bala & Prakriti</i>)
4.	Vamana Karma	With <i>Madanaphala pippali</i>
5.	Virechana Karma	With <i>Trivrit Lehya</i>
6.	Basti Karma	<i>Dashamoola ksheera basti, Madhutailika Basti, Bruhatyadi Yapana basti (Vrushya Bastis).</i> ^[13] , <i>Uttara basti</i>
7.	Nasya Karma	<i>Bruhmana or Shodhana Nasya</i> can be advised.

Table No. 3: Blueprint of Panchakarma In Pre-Conceptional Health Preservation.

Sl.No.	Karma	Description
1.	Deepana & Pachana	Hot water boiled with Shunti or Dhanyaka
2.	Snehana Karma	Ghrita can be advised (Except <i>Ksheerada avastha, vatarogas, Krishna Balaka</i>)
3.	Swedana Karma	Any of the eight <i>swedana karmas</i> mentioned by <i>Kashyapa</i> (especially <i>Hasta sweda</i> or <i>Pata sweda</i>) Eg- <i>Shashtika shaali pinda swedana</i> acts as <i>Balya</i> and <i>Bruhmanakara</i> .
4.	Vamana Karma	Indicated in children above 10 years of age.
5.	Virechana Karma	A Mridu Virechana is advised (The drug should be palatable) eg- <i>Draksha, Ksheera</i>
6.	Basti Karma	A <i>Matra basti</i> ¹⁴ or <i>basti</i> which is having <i>Taila</i> more than <i>Kashaya</i> should be indicated.
7.	Nasya Karma	<i>Pratimarsha Nasya</i> . ¹⁵ can be given, <i>Bruhmana Nasya</i> can be indicated

DEMOGRAPHIC WISE SCOPE AND CHALLENGES

Demographic/Region	Urban	Rural	Sub-Urban	Metropolitan
Children	Lifestyle diseases	Malnutrition, Hygiene issues	Mixed	Over exposure to stress, Pollution
Adults	Work stress, poor diet	Limited facilities	Less/ Moderate awareness	High lifestyle disorders
Elderly	Joint issues, Insomnia, senile disorders	Lack of expert care	Moderate accessibility	Expensive treatments
Women	Hormonal imbalance	Post-natal care gaps	Moderate access	High stress, Infertility
Challenges	Awareness, Accessibility	Lack of trained professionals	Affordability and awareness	Expensive, Time constraints
Scope	Look for Vyadhi severity and plan treatment accordingly	Preventive care plays a major role	Look for Vyadhi severity and plan treatment accordingly	Corporate wellness programmes and time constraint treatment plans.

CONCEPT OF KRAMATAH SHODHANA

BLUEPRINT OF PANCHAKARMA IN SWASTHA FOR PRESERVATION OF HEALTH.

VAMANA KARMA	
DAYS	TREATMENT
Day-1 To Day-3	* <i>Pachana and Deepana</i> with <i>Agnitundi vati 2-2-2</i> (or) <i>Chitrakadi vati 2-2-2</i> (or) <i>Shunti Churna ½ tsp TID</i> * In cases of <i>medura, mamsala, bhuri shleshma, Udwartana</i> with <i>Tripahala and Poorvakarma</i> followed by <i>Bashpa Sweda</i> or <i>Parisheka</i> can be adopted.

Day-4 Day-5 Day-6 Day-7	Snehapana with the Ghrita or Taila 1 st day of snehapana- Approx 30ml 2 nd day of snehapana- Approx 70ml 3 rd day of snehapana- Approx 110ml 4 th day of snehapana- Approx 150ml According to Agni and Koshta If samyak snigdha lakshanas are attained Snehapana can be stopped.
Day-8	Vishrama Kala of 1 day * Sarvanga Abhyanga with Taila * Sarvanga Parisheka or Bashpa Sweda.
Day-9	Vamana Karma (Considered as 1 st day of Vamana) Madanaphala sheeta kashaya or any Vamaka dravya * Look for the type of Shuddhi in terms of vegiki, maniki, antiki and laingiki.
Day-10 To Day-13 or Day-15	Based on the type of Shuddhi attained, Samsarjana Krama is advised¹⁷.
VIRECHANA KARMA	
Day-14 To Day-16	Gap for 3days
Day-17 Day-18 Day-19	Snehapana with Taila or ghrita to be started on 9 th day after Vamana Karma. 1 st day of Snehapana= 30ml 2 nd day of Snehapana= 75ml 3 rd day of Snehapana= 120ml If samyak snigdha lakshanas are attained Snehapana can be stopped.
Day-20 To Day-22	Vishrama Kala for 3days. * Sarvanga Abhyanga with taila. * Sarvanga Bashpa sweda or parisheka.
Day-23	<i>Virechana Karma</i> on the 15 th day after <i>Vamana Karma</i> with prescribed <i>Aushadha</i> In a proper dosage With proper <i>Anupana</i> . Look for the type of <i>Shuddhi</i> in terms of <i>vegiki, maniki, antiki and laingiki</i> .
Day- 24 To Day-27 or Day-29	Based on the type of <i>Shuddhi</i> attained, <i>Samsarjana Krama</i> is advised.
BASTI KARMA	
Day- 28 To Day- 30	Gap for 3days
Type of Basti has to be choosen like <i>Yapana basti</i> which can be given in a <i>swastha</i> in a pattern of <i>Yoga/ Kala/ Karma basti</i> and to be started on 9 th day after <i>Virechana Karma</i> Basti should be administered after , * <i>Sarvanga Abhyanga with Taila</i> * <i>Sarvanga Parisheka or Bashpa sweda</i>	
Day-31	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>
Day-32	<i>Niruha Basti</i>
Day-33	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>
Day-34	<i>Niruha Basti</i>
Day-35	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>
Day-36	<i>Niruha Basti</i>
Day-37	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>
Day-38	<i>Anuvasana Basti</i>
NASYA KARMA	
Day- 39 To Day- 54	Gap for 16days (<i>Dwiguna pariharakala</i>)

Day-55 To Day-57	<i>Nasya Karma</i> to be started on the 17 th day after <i>Basti Karma</i> . <i>Mukha Abhyanga</i> <i>Sthanika Swedana</i> with a cotton cloth dipped in <i>Ushna Jala</i> or <i>Sthanika Nadi sweda</i> Consider the type of <i>Nasya- Aushadha- Dosage</i> .
------------------------	--

CHALLENGES OF PANCHAKARMA BLUEPRINT

Sl.No	CHALLENGE	HOW TO OVERCOME
1.	Myth about snehapana increasing blood cholesterol levels	<i>Jangama Sneha</i> (Saturated fats) are used in moderation for the medicinal purpose. Whereas <i>sthavara Sneha</i> (Unsaturated fats) is indicated in conditions like, <i>pravruddha sleshma medaskaschala sthulah..</i> Acharyas have mentioned different utilization of <i>Sneha</i> according to the suitable <i>Vyadhis</i> . Judicious use of <i>Sneha</i> will not cause any complications.
2.	Concept of electrolyte imbalance	The modern day literature suggest that purgation and emesis leads to electrolyte imbalance and loss of electrolytes or even hypotension. But the procedure when done according to classical manner starting with <i>poorvakarma</i> , <i>pradhanakarma</i> and <i>samsarjana karma</i> will not let the person land up into <i>vyapads</i> . However if <i>atiyoga</i> occurs one can observe the features of <i>Ap Dhatu kshaya</i> and henceforth should start treatment accordingly. If there is <i>ayoga</i> , one can advise <i>Tarpanadi kramas</i> ¹⁸
3.	concept of food restriction post panchakarma	One of the primary goals of Panchakarma is to balance the <i>Agni</i> . <i>Samsarjana Krama</i> has to be adopted to restore and balance the <i>Agni</i> . After <i>Samshodhana Karmas</i> there will be <i>Kaya Agni Mandyata</i> . Thus Acharya Susruta has said, <i>Tatkaala eva mandah; kramena tu deerto bhavati iti doshaprasangah</i> ¹⁹ ..Here the term <i>Kramena</i> refers to order of <i>Peyadi Samsarjana Krama</i> . After <i>Vamana</i> and <i>Virechana</i> there's <i>mandagni</i> , thus to normalize this <i>Peyadi samsarjana krama</i> has to be advised.
4.	Individualized treatment needs	Each person's health profile is unique, requiring personalized assessment and treatment planning. <i>Ayurveda</i> outlines the concept as <i>Karyam Dhatusamyam</i> ²⁰ . Planning of the treatment according to individual's financial condition also poses as a challenge. By the help of <i>Prakriti</i> , <i>Dosha Avastha</i> of the <i>Rugna</i> etc..Treatment has to be planned. Eg- Before Starting <i>Snehapana</i> for <i>Shodhana</i> Assessment of <i>Koshta</i> , <i>Agni</i> , <i>Bala</i> , of the rogi helps for a successful treatment and thus attaining <i>Dhatusamyata</i> . Financially struggling- Government schemes for an affordable and Highly efficacy treatment.
5.	Difficulty in following Ashtamahadoshakara varjya bhavas	In current era, it is a task to avoid eight factors that aggravate the <i>Doshas</i> during and after panchakarma. Patient should be counselled about these factors prior, during and after <i>Shodhana</i> . The consequences of practicing these <i>Varjya Bhavas</i> ²¹ should be made clear. Eg- * <i>Ucchair-bhashya</i> causes <i>Urdwa dehapeeda</i> * <i>Ratha Kshobha</i> causes <i>Sarva deha peeda</i> (Physician should make it clear about the mode of transportation patient uses and advise accordingly)

		* <i>Diva Swapna</i> will cause headache by increasing the <i>Kapha Dosh</i> .
6.	Difficulty in distinguishing what <i>ritu</i> and undergo which <i>shodhana</i>.	In the present era, it's becoming difficult to distinguish between seasons due to the unpredictable and rapid transitions in weather patterns. Thus randomly advising <i>Vamana</i> , <i>Virechana</i> etc is not valid. Acharya Sushruta in <i>Ritucharyadhyaya</i> , explained about <i>Avyapanna Ritu lakshana</i> for individual <i>Ritu</i> ²² . Eg- * <i>Hemanta Ritu</i> - The direction of <i>Vayu</i> is from <i>Uttara dik</i> , <i>Sheeta</i> in nature, <i>Himanaddha jalashaya</i> etc.. * <i>Greeshma ritu</i> - <i>Teekshna kiranas</i> from sun, Wind from <i>Nairuthya dik</i> etc.

DISCUSSION

A Swastha person not undergoing Shodhana periodically is considered to be *Bheshaja dweshi* and will invite *Vyadhis*. Acharya Vagbhata has mentioned about the factors responsible for *Roga- upadana*.^[23] They are *Vegodeerana*, *Vega Dharana*, *Shodhana*, *Bruhmana*. If these 5 factors are not taken into consideration during *Aniyata kala* (Disease causing time) it will lead to manifestation of a *Vyadhi*. The basic contribution of panchakarma is that it removes vitiated *Doshas* from the body and provides *Samshuddhi* at two levels,

1. Gross level- Various organs are thoroughly cleansed
2. Cellular level- At the level of cells, cell membranes etc.

What's more challenging is giving of *Snehapana* prior to *Shodhana*. For such individuals, an alternative like Soft gel capsules can be adopted. Although there's still a need of Standard research for utilization of *Sneha dravyas* for the purpose of *Shodhana*. There are various *Taila* soft gel capsules available in market, but them favouring the purpose of *Shodhananga Snehapana* is absolutely nil.

After the *Panchakarma* therapy, biochemicals in the body return to normal levels, according to clinical studies. Public health concerns can be done if *Panchakarma* is well supported with strong scientific evidence and confirmation.^[24] In a study it was found that, Catalase activity increases and Lipid peroxidase reaction decreases as *Vamana* goes on. The concept of Microbiome is especially considered in *Virechana Karma*. The whole environment of Intestine changes after a *Virechana Karma*. *Samsarjana Krama* followed by *Virechana*, provides a new microbiome environment in gut.

Niruha Basti Karma facilitates peristaltic action and enhances absorption of nutrients from the caecum and ascending colon. *Mustadi Yapana basti* is seen to reduce the TB specific IgG and IgM significantly. *Anuvasana basti* influences the immune function of the body by production of T helper cells, leucocytes, cytokines and modulation of lymph mechanism. It is essential to have the knowledge of *Shodhana* or else it may cause *Upadravas* like *Shotha*, *Kushta* etc. Thus it is required to assess different factors prior to *shodhana*. In a Procedure

like *Nasya*, the medicine administered through *Nasa* reach upto *sringataka Marma* and spreads all over *Urdhwajatru* and eliminates the *Gambheera Doshas*. *Rakthamokshana* is ponder as *Ardha chikitsa* and due to *Asraya asrayi bhava*, it acts on *Pitta dosha* too. *Rakthamokshana* stimulates haemopoiesis and thus aids in increasing immunity. For busy individuals, *Panchakarma* can be adapted by shortening the duration, offering flexible scheduling and targeting specific treatments. Opting flexible timings either early morning or evening once in year for a proper *Deha Samshodhana* can be done without disrupting their workday.

CONCLUSION

Panchakarma holds immense potential for promoting health in modern era through its focus on *Samshodhana* and balance of *Tridoshas*. The scope of *Panchakarma* extends to both preventive and curative healthcare, addressing lifestyle disorders, chronic conditions and mental well-being. Challenges such as Standardization, scientific validation, integration with modern healthcare systems and awareness among the public need to be addressed for widespread adoption. A balanced approach combining traditional wisdom with modern research can ensure its effectiveness and relevance in today's health paradigm. Thus to conclude, **From pollution to purification, let Panchakarma preserve your health.**

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Shaareera sthana, Chapter Shareera vichaya Shaareera adhyaya, Verse. 29. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 336.
2. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Shaareera sthana, Chapter Khuddikagarbhavakranti Shaareera adhyaya, Verse. 30. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 336.
3. Vagbhata, Arunadatta, Hemadri, Sutrasthana, Ayushkaamiya adhyaya, Verse 14, In: Harisadashiva shastry Paradkar bhisagacharya (Edi.) Ashtanga hrudaya with Sarvanga Sundara and Ayurveda

- Rasayana Commentary, Reprint Edition 2021, Varanasi Chaukambha Orientalia, 217.
4. Vagbhata, Arunadatta, Hemadri, Sutrasthana, Doshadivijnaniya adhyaya, Verse 34, In: Harisadashiva shastry Paradkar bhashagacharya(Edi.) Ashtanga hrudaya with Sarvanga Sundara and Ayurveda Rasayana Commentary, Reprint Edition 2021, Varanasi Chaukambha Orientalia, 217.
 5. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Chikitsa sthana, Chapter Grahani chikitsa adhyaya, Verse. 4. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 512.
 6. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Chikitsa sthana, Chapter Grahani chikitsa adhyaya, Verse. 29. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 688.
 7. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Sutra sthana, Chapter Trisreshaniya adhyaya, Verse. 43. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 73.
 8. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter Vamana virechana sadhya upadrava chikitsa Adhyaya, Verse 12. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 517.
 9. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter Vamana virechana sadhya upadrava chikitsa Adhyaya, Verse 27. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 519.
 10. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter Niruhakrama chikitsa Adhyaya, Verse 14. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 541.
 11. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter Dhooma nasya kavalagraha chikitsa Adhyaya, Verse 50. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 557.
 12. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Sutra Sthana, Chapter Shonitavarnaneeya Sutra Adhyaya, Verse 34. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 65.
 13. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Siddhi sthana, Chapter Uttarabasti Siddhi adhyaya, Verse. 16. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 732
 14. Vagbhata, Arunadatta, Hemadri, Sutrasthana, Bastividhi adhyaya, Verse 68, In: Harisadashiva shastry Paradkar bhashagacharya(Edi.) Ashtanga hrudaya with Sarvanga Sundara and Ayurveda Rasayana Commentary, Reprint Edition 2021, Varanasi Chaukambha Orientalia, 283.
 15. Vagbhata, Arunadatta, Hemadri, Sutrasthana, Nasyavidhi adhyaya, Verse 26, In: Harisadashiva shastry Paradkar bhashagacharya(Edi.) Ashtanga hrudaya with Sarvanga Sundara and Ayurveda Rasayana Commentary, Reprint Edition 2021, Varanasi Chaukambha Orientalia, 292.
 16. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Siddhi sthana, Chapter Kalpana Siddhi adhyaya, Verse. 20. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 680.
 17. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter Aturopadrava chikitsa Adhyaya, Verse 3. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 549.
 18. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Siddhi sthana, Chapter Vamanavirechanavyapat Siddhi adhyaya, Verse. 25. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 705.
 19. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Chikitsa Sthana, Chapter Aturopadrava chikitsa Adhyaya, Verse 3. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia 549.
 20. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Vimana sthana, Chapter Rogabhashagatiya Vimana adhyaya, Verse. 89. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 274.
 21. Agnivesha, Charaka, Chakrapanidatta, Siddhi sthana, Chapter Uttarabasti Siddhi adhyaya, Verse. 14. In: Acharya YT (Edi.), Charaka samhita with Ayurveda deepika commentary Reprint Edition 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 730.
 22. Sushruta, Dalhana, Gayadasa. Sutra Sthana, Chapter Rutucharya Sutra Adhyaya, Verse 21. In: Yt Acharya Narayana ram(Edi.). Sushruta Samhita with Nibandhasangraha, and Nyayachandrika commentary Reprint Edition: 2023. Varanasi: Chaukambha Orientalia. 28.
 23. Vagbhata, Arunadatta, Hemadri, Sutrasthana, Roganutpadaniya adhyaya, Verse 1, In: Harisadashiva shastry Paradkar bhashagacharya(Edi.) Ashtanga hrudaya with Sarvanga Sundara and Ayurveda Rasayana Commentary, Reprint Edition 2021, Varanasi Chaukambha Orientalia, 52.

24. Manjunatharao SV, Shreyas DM, Kiran M Goud. "Conceptual Review on the role of Panchakarma practice in Swastha". *Journal of Ayurveda and Integrated Medical Science*, 2024; 12: 199-204. Available at, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/389654629_Conceptual_Review_on_the_role_of_Panchakarma_practice_in_Swastha (Accessed: 31 July 2025)